

The Benefits of a Silvopoultry System and the Supports Available in Ireland

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Silvopoultry system Establishment (Photo: Teagasc)
Poultry foraging in the foreground of a recently established site.

Poultry farm productivity, land management, and animal welfare in Ireland can benefit from poultry silvopasture systems (silvopoultry). Trees provide wind and rain shelter, reducing stress and boosting egg and meat production, especially in free-range systems. Natural cover encourages foraging and dust-bathing while protecting birds from predators. Poultry grazing helps to control weeds and pests, lowering chemical use. Their manure enriches soil, and scratching aerates the ground, preventing erosion. The combination of poultry with native trees like oak, alder, and hazel enhance ecosystem services.

Primary income comes from free-range eggs and meat, in high demand among ethical consumers, while organic certification can boost marketability. Setting up a system requires selecting trees and designing paddocks for rotational grazing. Mulberry, hazel, autumn olive, apple, pear, elderberry, and stone pine provide shelter and feed, while nitrogen-fixing trees improve soil. Trees should be planted in winter, protected with guards, and supported by ground cover to prevent erosion.

Good paddock management is key. Portable fencing controls grazing, prevents overuse, and allows vegetation recovery. Mobile or static housing provides shelter and predator protection. Hardy breeds suit outdoor systems. Poultry manure must be managed to prevent nutrient overloads. Birds forage on fruit, seeds, and insects, lowering feed costs while improving egg and meat quality. Trees absorb ammonia, stabilize soil, and improve water retention, reducing flooding.

For mobile housing, trees are planted in rows with pasture alleys for movement and silage potential. In wet areas, wooded paddocks with fenced paths are used. Birds must learn to use nest boxes before tree cover is introduced. For static housing, trees planted downwind absorb ammonia, with spacing encouraging ranging and reducing nutrient build-up. Open sight lines help birds explore evenly.

Ireland's Forest Type 8 – Agroforestry scheme supports tree planting with food production. Eligible land (0.5+ ha, 20m+ width) requires 400+ trees ha⁻¹. Approved species include oak, sycamore, and cherry. Converted land is classified as forest under the Forestry Act 2014. Landowners receive €8,555/ha (excluding fencing) for establishment costs and €975 ha⁻¹ annually for 10 years, available to farmers and non-farmers.

References

Westaway, S., Kling, C., & Smith, J. (2018). A comparison of the performance of three sward mixtures sown under trees in a silvopoultry system in the UK. *Agroforestry Systems*, 92(4), 1009–1018.

Smith, J., & Wells, A. (2001). *Silvo-Poultry: An Agroforestry System for Organic Chicken Production at Sheepdrove Organic Farm*. The Organic Research Centre.

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